

ON THE NONLINEAR DYNAMICS OF INTERACTING GENETICALLY MODIFIED T CELLS AND TUMOR CELLS

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Abstract

The genetically modified T cells are developed by transferring certain genes into the T cell of the blood sample collected from the tumor patient, able to produce expression of T cell receptor (TCR) that has boosted immune response. These TCRs are capable to identify, track, bind with tumor cells and annihilate tumor cells like two species pre-predator dynamics. This dynamics is modeled by modified two species interacting prey and predator model of Lotka-Volterra with two independent variables, genetically altered T cells as immune cells and tumor cells. The sensitive analysis of this model of a pair of ordinary nonlinear ordinary differential equations is studied and found the respective nonlinear dynamics is stable and suitable for successful elimination of tumor growth.

Keyword: Receptor, Immune, Annihilation, Cytokine, Effector cell, Retrovirus, Adenovirus, Painleve, Parameter, Resonance, Algorithm, Therapeutic, Polypeptide.

01. Introduction

Innate and adaptive immune actions are the two types of response of the immune system that control growth and displacement of the tumor cells [1]-[7]. Cytokines are cell signaling proteins capable to regulate growth, mutations, suppression, and activation of various immune cells. Cytokines like $TGF\beta$, $IL - 23$ are showing pro-tumor and anti-tumor properties. The active cells of immune

system collectively called as “immune cells” of “effector cells”. Even after activation, identification and annihilation of the most of the tumor cells, some of the tumor cells may escape and they start proliferate more aggressively [1]-[7].. Such case external adjuvant or methods are necessary to enhance the immune system to overcome the immunosuppressive behavior of the tumor cells or direct annihilation of all remaining cancer cells. This defects of immune system of the incomplete annihilation of the tumor cells sometimes due to some errors in the genetic makeup of the patient. [1]-[7].

Whenever a disease or disorder is due to malfunction of the genetic makeup of a patient then by correcting that genetic makeup by with or without suitable drugs without surgical approach is the curative approach in Gene Therapy (GT) [1]-[7]. For GT there are two types of methods are using, introduce a new gene into the cells for boosting immunity or introduce a non faulty copy of the defective gene when faulty gene is the causative factor of that disease or disorder of the patient. For modifying the genetic code is applicable when the loss of function of the critical protein that control the boosting of immunity of the body is the causative factor of the disease. For this two types interventions are using, gene transfer therapy and genetic editing. In gene transfer therapy new gene material is added into the cell. In gene editing therapy new genetic material genome editing tools are using to modify the existing DNA of the cell in order to correct the malfunctions. For this turn on a gene that stopped its proper functions or turn off a gene that functions in faulty manner or cut off a part of DNA that responsible for the disorder or disease [1]-[8].

CRISPR-Cas9 is generally adopted method [3],[6],[12]-[16]] for genetic editing therapy, for that a carrier called vector is using for transfer the new gene material into the nucleus of the cell. Two commonly using vectors are retroviruses and adenoviruses, where retroviruses is RNA virus that has reverse transcriptase activity which enables to synthesize a complementary DNA (eg. Moloney’s murine leukemia virus) [3], [12]-[16]. In this process DNA is not integrated into the chromosome, so that no significant change occurs in hereditary makeup of the patient [3],[10]-[11]-[16]. These vectors are directly

administered as injections or given intravenously (by IV) into that particular tissue in the body. Another method is vector inserted into a sample collected from the body then transfer to the body. Non virus vectors like bacteria, nano particles, liposomes , are also using for gene editing [3],[15][16] . The selection of suitable vectors depends on the characteristics like replication of the vector, genetic combinations structure, duration of transgenic expression, target specificity, sustained gene delivery ,biocompatibility etc.

Dendritic cell can be genetically modified to express tumor associated antigens (TAA) whereas, T cell modified to T cell receptors (TCRs) ,by which tumor specific immune response can be boosted and that enhancing the capacity for searching, identifying ,tracking, binding and annihilating the cancer cells [3]-[6][17]-[21]. This modification is carried out by specific genes are inserted into the T cells of the blood sample collected from the patient[6],[17]-[21] That TCRs are able to identify and binding cancer cells more effectively and annihilate cancer cells. This process of tracking and annihilation of the cancer cell by genetically modified T cells to TCR is similar to the prey and predator two species interacting nonlinear process [17]-[21]. For which mathematical model is known with modified Lotka-Volterra's model [6], [17]-[21]

In this study the sensitivity analysis of above modified Lotka –Volterra's model for interacting TCRs and tumor cells [6],[18],[19] is studied by Painleve's method developed for the system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations.

02. Mathematical Model for Interacting TCR the Genetically Modified T cell and Tumor Cell in Terms of Modified Lotka-Volterra's Nonlinear Model

When immune response is not sufficient for annihilating the invader tumor cells, by genetically modifying the T cells to T cell receptors (TCR) having tumor specific enhanced immune response can be used to fight against the tumor cells. TCRs are developed by inserting tumor specific genes into the blood sample collected from the patient. Then the searching , identifying ,tracking, binding and annihilating the tumor cells by TCRs is much similar to the dynamics that of two species prey and predator nonlinear model of Lotka-Volteera's model. The

nonlinear dynamics of interacting TCRs and tumor cells is studied as a modified form of two species model [6],[18]-[21] ,

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = a_0 + a_1 C - a_2 I + \frac{a_3 I}{I+a_4}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = a_5 C(1 - a_6 C) - a_6 C - \frac{a_7 IC}{C+a_8}. \quad (2)$$

Where $I(t)$ is the immune cells TCRs population, $C(t)$ is the tumor cells population. *Parameter* a_0 is the influx rate of immune cells, parameter a_1 is the antigenicity of tumor cells, a_2 is the natural death rate of immune cells, a_3 is the growth rate of immune cells, a_4 is the half-saturation constant of immunity cells population $I(t)$ proliferation. Parameters a_5 growth rate and a_6 is the reciprocal carrying capacity of tumor cells and immune cells populations respectively. Parameter a_7 is the gene therapy treatment-induced cell-kill rate, a_8 is the half-saturation constant so that the term $\frac{-a_7 IC}{C+a_8}$ represents the effect of annihilation of tumor cells $C(t)$ in the gene therapy. Whereas, the term $a_5 C(1 - a_6 C)$ represents growth of tumor cells. In this study using Painleve Property analysis sensitivity analysis of the dynamics of the above model is studied,

03. Sensitivity analysis by Painleve’s property analysis (PPA) of a system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations, ARS algorithm.

In the study of nonlinear dynamical systems, chaos has measured by an extreme sensitivity of the solutions to the control parameter associated with the initial conditions. Equations whose solutions are free from any chaotic behaviour are called ‘completely Integrable’, that are characterized by regular or predictable behaviour for all values of initial conditions and for all time. Whereas, in ‘Non-integrable’ systems, their regions in the phase space of their dependent variables the motion is irregular and chaotic. This type of study initiated by Sonya Kowaleveskaya [22] in the context of rotating bodies, is the first attempt in dynamical systems associated with singularities.

There are two types singularities, first one called fixed singularity in which their location of singularity determined by the equation itself, second type is the movable singularity where its locations depends on the initial conditions. Fixed singularity type is absent in linear equations, but in nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs) both types of singularities are possible.

Painleve' found[23] three types of second order nonlinear ODEs with only movable singularities are poles. Then Gambier added three more such types in 1916 and concluded no their cases arising in second order nonlinear ordinary differential equations [23], this property is called Painleve' Property (PP) . An algorithm developed by Ablowitz, Ramani and Segur called ARS algorithm [24] ,[25]for nonlinear ordinary first order differential equations that admits singularities as movable branch points, either algebraic or logarithmic .That ARS algorithm is using in this study for PPA analysis of (1) and (2).

Let us consider a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) of the form

$$\frac{du^i}{dt} = F_i(u^1, u^2, \dots, u^n), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

Then we are searching for dominant behaviour of the solutions in the neighbourhood of a movable singularity of the form

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i}, \quad \text{where } \tau = (t_0 - t). \quad (4)$$

Then there are three steps for the ARS algorithm;

Step 01

Substitute equation (4) in (3) and find all possible values ρ_i , for which two or more leading ordered terms in each equation balance each other, and the rest can be ignored for each such choice of the ρ_i . Also find all possible values of α_i .

Step 02

In step 02, keep only the leading ordered balancing terms of step 01 and ignore rest and substitute

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i} (1 + \gamma_i \tau^r) \quad (3)$$

All product terms of γ_i are to be omitted, then system reduced to

$$Q(r) \cdot \gamma = 0, \quad \text{where } \gamma = (\gamma_1 \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n). \quad (4),$$

Where $Q(r)$ is a $(n \times n)$ matrix in which r entering only in its diagonal elements, almost linearly. Then find the roots of the determinant of

$$\text{Det } Q(r) = 0, \quad (5)$$

These values of r are called resonances. Resonance determines the number of arbitrary constants exist in the system of ODEs (3). Resonance $r = -1$ is related to the location of the one free constant, namely t_0 the point of the singularity and that always appear in the roots of (5).

The resonance $r = 0$ corresponds to the coefficient of one of the the leading ordered terms being arbitrary. Any resonance with real valued and $r > 0$ but not an integer indicates at $t = t_0$ is a movable singularity when ρ_i are negative integers,

We have to evaluate all possible distinct $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued integer resonances. Less than $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued distinct integer resonances implies system has no PP property.

If R is the largest positive and integer valued resonance r , then substitute in the Laurent's series expansions,

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i} + \sum_{m=1}^R \alpha_i^m \tau^{\rho_i+m}, \quad (6)$$

and verify the compactibility conditions if necessary for finding all free constants required integrability condition.

04. Sensitivity Analysis of Mathematical Model of Interacting TCRs and Tumor cells by ARS Algorithm

Equations (1) and (2) can be rewritten as

$$(I+a_4)\frac{dI}{dt} = a_0(I+a_4)+a_1C(I+a_4) - a_2I(I+a_4) + a_3I, \quad (7)$$

$$(C+a_8)\frac{dC}{dt} = a_5C(C+a_8)(1-a_6C) - a_6C(C+a_8) - a_7IC. \quad (8)$$

According to the above ARS algorithm the balancing dominating terms of (7) and (8) are ,

$$a_4\frac{dI}{dt} = a_1IC, \quad (9)$$

and

$$a_8\frac{dC}{dt} = a_7IC. \quad (10)$$

Substitute ,

$$I = \alpha\tau^p, \text{ and } C = \beta\tau^q, \quad (11)$$

in (9) and (11) ,then the possible values of α, β, p and q are,

$$\alpha = \frac{a_8}{a_7}, \beta = -\frac{a_4}{a_1}, p = -1 \text{ and } q = -1. \quad (12)$$

For finding resonance values r substitute ,

$$I = \alpha\tau^p (1 + \gamma\tau^r) \text{ and } C = \beta\tau^q(1 + \delta\tau^r) \quad (13)$$

in (8) and (10) ,get values of resonances r in terms γ and δ as,

$$r\gamma + \delta = 0, \quad (14)$$

and

$$r\delta + \gamma = 0. \quad (15)$$

Equations (14) and (15) in terms of matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} r & 1 \\ 1 & r \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \delta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

gives values of resonances r from the determinant equation,

$$\begin{vmatrix} r & 1 \\ 1 & r \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (17)$$

From (19) gets values of resonances as $r = -1$ and $r = +1$.

Since $p = -1$, $q = -1$ and resonances $r = \pm 1$ are all integers, the dynamics represents the system of differential equations (1) and (2) satisfies PPA according to the ARS algorithm.

05. Conclusion

Compared to other therapies like Chemotherapy, Radiation therapy the immunotherapy has advantages like very specific in targeting the tumor cells alone and healthy cells unaffected [26],[32],[33], and side effects are very little. In other therapies tumor cells are tricking the immune system by immune editing and suppressing immunogenic clones and escape from annihilation, but in the enhanced immune response of TCR by genetic modification capable to identify, track and annihilate even such escaped tumor cells. The immune response to tumor cells has important factor and it is related to antigenicity of tumor cells so that when immunogenicity of tumor cells are boosting, that more identifiable and tracking by immune system [28], [32],[33]. It is observed that high immune response is triggered by TCR and TGF- β when antigenicity of tumor cells are increasing. Even then an optimum amount of antigenicity of tumor cells exists for the maximum amount of possible immune response [10], [30],[31].

There are two types of immune response to external pathogens or invader cells like tumor cells, Non-specific immune response (Innate immunity) and the other is Specific-immune response (Adoptive immunity). In nonspecific immune

response once pathogen (abnormal or invader cell) identified the immune system either counteracts with its non-specific fighters such as phagocyte-toxic leukocytes and natural killer cells like monocytes, neutrophils, mast cells and macrophages or using pathogen specific fighters such as B and T cells. This general immune response is not specific to a particular pathogen. Whereas, in adoptive immune response when type of pathogen identifies according to the type of antigen present on them then activate respective antigen-specific immune cells such as helper, effector and memory cells and annihilate the pathogen by active immune cells (effector cells)[33].

There are many methods [12]-[16] are using in gene therapy like transfer of genes into a sample collected from that patient's cells outside the body (ex vivo gene therapy), transfer of gene directly to the cells inside the body of that patient (in vivo gene therapy), direct annihilation of malfunctioned cells that cause disease either by inserting toxic gene into the diseased cells or using carrier vector that has self-destruction properties inside the tumor and that activate the killing of tumor cells, targeted inhibition of gene expression is used in order to block the expression of a faulty gene. For restoring the function of a faulty gene by the targeted gene mutation correction at the genetic level is used by homologous recombination or at messenger RNA (mRNA) level by utilizing therapeutic RNA editing etc[12]-[16].

The cytokine TGF- β regulates the tumor-antigen expression that controls the activation of effector cells, it is a regulatory polypeptide that regulates growth, differentiation, adhesion, apoptosis, angiogenesis in the tumor microenvironment. Inside the tumor microenvironment TGF- β regulates the small interfering RNA (siRNA mediated degradation of messenger RNA (mRNA) and the production of TGF- β can be modulated by altering gene expression [6],[12], [16]. Cytokine TGF- β promotes as well as suppress the growth of tumor and so its optimum function is an essential task in the treatment of tumor, that can be done by modifying the expression of genes [6],

Using CRISPER-Cas9 genome editing can be done instead of inserting a new genetic material at specific location in the genome, for this carrier vector is using to deliver the genetic material that either injected or given intravenously (IV) directly into a selected tissue in the patient or a sample collected from the body of the patient, expose to the genetic material in the lab and returned to the body of the patient. This modified gene inserted by suitable vector able to make a functioning protein or editing molecules for correcting a DNA error. There are few viral and non viral vectors in which adenoassociated Viruses have shown better results for in vivo gene transfer [12]-[16].

In associated to annihilation of faulty cells, the gene therapy the procedure is inserting a specific antigen coding gene that activate and boost immune cells for searching, identifying, targeting and annihilation of the tumor cells. For this activation of the immune cells, certain cytokine encoded gene added to the vector and inserted in the diseased cell or in the healthy cell. Then the enhanced immune response identify, target and annihilate the diseased cells by binding. For this purpose the therapeutic genes to be delivered to specific targets, for cancer these targets are tumor cells, antigen preserving cells, blood progenitor cells, T cells, fibroblasts, muscle cells etc[12]-[16].

T cells can be genetically modified to TCR has enhanced tumor specific immune responses [3], [8]-[17]. These modified T cells to TCR are able to identify, target and binding then annihilate tumor cells [6]. Such dynamics mathematically modeled as modified prey-predator model of two species [18]-, [21], [29] in which immune cells and tumor cells are the predator and prey variables respectively so formed a pair of first order nonlinear ordinary differential equations (1) and (2). In the sensitivity analysis of the model equations (1) and (2) found that dynamics system satisfied all conditions of ARS algorithm for long time scale nonlinear stability. Hence this study conclude that mathematical model suggested for gene therapy corresponds to interaction of immune cell cells TCRs and tumor cells modeled as (1) and (2) having long time scale stable dynamics.

The advantages of gene therapy (GT) are, able to cure disease by addition of deletion of genes or by replacing a mutated gene with corrected gene, in cancer management GT is used to annihilate tumor cells more effectively, in GT the gene expression can be regulated, and therapeutic protein is continuously developed within the patient body itself is an advantage compared to other therapies.

References

- [1]. B.Alberts, A.Johnson, J.Lewis, M.Raff, K.roberts, P.walter.,” Helper T cells and lymphocytes activation” . in “Molecular Biology of the Cell”, 4th edition (Garland Science ,2002).
- [3]. J.E.Talmadge, K.H.Cowan, in ”Gene therapy in Oncology, in Abeloeff’s Clinical Oncology”, Elsevier, Amsterdam, p.470-485 (2020).
- [4]. M.M. Hulou, C.F. Cho, E.A. Chiccca, R. Bjerkvig, in “ Experimental therapies : gene therapies and oncolytic viruses, in Gliomas Handbook of Clinical Neurology, vol.134, p.183-197, Elsevier ,Amsterdam (2016) .
- [5]. S.A. Kaliberov, D.J. Buchsbaum, in “Cancer treatment with gene therapy and radiation therapy, Advance in Cancer Research, vol.115, p.221-263 (2012)
- [6]. Regina Padmanabhan, Nader Meskin, Ala-Eddin Al Moustafa, in “Mathematical Models of Cancer and Different Therapies” , Springer pub. ,Singapore (2021).
- [7]. K.E. Hellstrom, I.Hellstrom, in “Lymphocyte-mediated cytotoxicity and blocking serum activity to tumor antigen”, in “Advance in Immunology. Vol.18” (elsvier, Amsterdam) p.209-277 (1974).
- [8]. F.D.Barkar, “Recent developments in oncology, immunotherapy, adverse effects Part 2”. Jr.Nurse Prac. **14**(4), p. 256-266 (2018).
- [9]. A.Rivaz ,M.Azizian ,M.Soltani, Various mathematical models of tumor growth with reference to cancer stemcells :a review “, Jr. Iran Jr.Sci. Technol. Trans. A:Sci.**43**(2), p.687-700 (2019).

- [10]. S.A.Rosenberg. “Decades in review-cancer immunotherapy ,entering the main stream of cancer treatment”. *Jr.Nat.Rev.Clin.Oncol.*, **11**, (11) p.630-645 (2014).
- [11]. C.A.Pennell, K.E.Ellis, “Demystifying cancer immunotherapy for lay audiences “, *Jr. Front.Immunol.* **10**, p.2488-2495(2019).
- [12]. M.F.Naso, B.Tomkowicz, W.L..Perry, W.R.Strohl, “Adeno-associated virus (AAV)as a vector for gene therapy”, *Jr.BioDrugs* ,**31**(4),p.317-334(2017).
- [13]. A.Nyamay Antu, M.Dumont, V.Kedinger , P.Erbacher,“Non-viral vector mediated gene delivery:the outsider to watch out for in gene therapy”,*Jr.Cell Gene Ther.Insights*,**5**, p.51-57(2019).
- [14]. Min Wang, Xinyu Zheng, Xiao –Mei Rao, Hongying Hao, Yanbin Dong , M.Kelly , McMasters, and H.Sam Zhou,“Adenoviral vector system for gene therapy “, *Jr.Gene Ther.Mol.Biol.* **9**, p.291-300 (2005).
- [15]. R.Alba,A.Bosch and M.Chillon ,”Gutless adenovirus: last generation adenovirus for gene therapy” *Jr.Gene therapy*, **12**,p.s18-s27, (2005)
- [16]. Yuanming Zhang and Jeffrey M.Bergelson,“ Adenovirus Receptors “ *Jr.Virol.* **79**(19),p.12125-12131 (2005).
- [17]. S.F.Kruger, B.L.Cadilha, M.V.Bergwelt Baildon, S.Endres,S,Kobold,“Challenges in clinical trial design for T cell-based cancer immunotherapy “, *Jr.Clin.Pharmacol.Ther.* ,**1**,p.47-49 (2020) .
- [18]. D.Kirschner, J.C.Panetta, “Modelling immunotherapy of the tumor-immune interaction” ,*Jr.Math.Biol.***37**(3),p. 235-252 (1998)
- [19]. B.Mukhopadhyay, R.Bhattacharyya,.” A nonlinear mathematical model of virus-tumor-immune system interaction : deterministic and stochastic analysis” *Jr. Stoch. Anal.Appl.***27**(2),p.409-429 (2009).
- [20]. E.Moreno Lampaya ,”Is cell competition relevant in cancer? “ *Jr.Nat.Rev.Cancer* , **8**, p.141-147(2008).

- [21]. R.Eftimie,J.L.Bramson, D.J.D.earn, “Interaction between the immune system and cancer : a brief review of non-spatial mathematical models .”,
Jr.Bull.Math.Biol. **73** (1),p.2-32(2011).
- [22]. Kowaleveskaya , Jr.Acta.Math. **14**, p.81-92 (1890).
- [23] . E.L.Ince, in “Ordinary Differential equations” , p.345 Dover,New York (1956).
- [24]. M.J.Ablowitz, A .Ramani, and H.Segur, ”A connection between nonlinear evolution equations and ordinary differential equations of P-type “ Jr.Math.Phys.**24**, p.522 -526 (1980).
- [25]. A.Ramani, B.Grammaticos, and Bountis, ”The Painleve property and singularity analysis of integrable and non-integrable systems”
Jr.Phys.Reports,**180**,p. 159-170 (1989).
- [26]. M.Robertson Tessi, A.El Kareh, .Goriely, “A mathematical model of tumor- immune interactions”, Jr.Theor.Biol.**294**, p.56-73 (2012).
- [27]. J.Maher,E.Davies, “Targeting cytotoxic T lymphocytes for cancer immunotherapy” , Jr. Cancer,**91**(5), p.817-821 (2004).
- [28]. S.Lee, K.Margolin,” Cytokine in cancer immunotherapy”, Jr.Cancer **3**(4), p.3856-3893 (2011).
- [29]. N.Bellomo, L.Preziosi,” Modelling and Mathematical problems related to tumor evolution and its interaction with immune system”
Jr.Math.Comput.Model.,**32**(3), p.413-452(2000).
- [30]. A.Ghaffari,N.Naserifar, “Optimal therapeutic protocol in cancer immunotherapy “, Jr.Comput.Biol.Med., **40**,(3),p.261-270 (2010).

- [31]. B.Piccoli, F. Castiglione, “Optimal vaccine scheduling in cancer immunotherapy”, Jr.Phys.A **370**(2),p.672-680 (2006).
- [32]. B.V.Baby .” Sensitivity analysis of a mathematical model of cancer dynamics under Chemotherapy”, Jr. Dalian Univ.Tech., **32**(8) ,p.717-732(2025).
- [33]. B.V. Baby. “ Sensitivity analysis of a mathematical model of the adoptive cellular therapy and cytokine injection for cancer management”, Jr.Dalian Univ.Tech. **32**(10),p.237-248 (2025).